

Theoretical study on the mechanism of synthesis of (4*R*,5*S*,8*as*)-4,5,8*a*-triphenylhexahydropyrimido[4,5-*d*]pyrimidine-2,7(1*H*,3*H*)-dione

Qi-Shan Hu*^a, Yun-Qing He^a and Lai-Cai Li^b

^aCollege of Chemistry and Chemical Engineering, Sichuan University of Arts and Science, Dazhou, 635711, People's Republic of China

E-mail : huqs@163.com

^bCollege of Chemistry and Material Science, Sichuan Normal University, Chengdu, 610066, People's Republic of China

Manuscript received online 30 June 2014, accepted 15 October 2016

Abstract : The mechanism of one-pot reaction of benzaldehyde, urea and acetophenone for the synthesis of (4*R*,5*S*,8*as*)-4,5,8*a*-triphenylhexahydropyrimido[4,5-*d*]pyrimidine-2,7(1*H*,3*H*)-dione catalyzed by protonic acid was investigated by density functional theory (DFT). The geometries and the frequencies of reactants, intermediates, transition states and products were calculated at the B3LYP/6-311G(d) level. The vibration analysis and the IRC analysis verified the authenticity of transition states. The reaction processes were confirmed by the changes of charge density at the bond-forming critical point. The results indicated that protonic acid is an effective catalyst in the synthesis of (4*R*,5*S*,8*as*)-4,5,8*a*-triphenylhexahydropyrimido[4,5-*d*]pyrimidine-2,7(1*H*,3*H*)-dione from benzaldehyde, urea and acetophenone. The activation energy of reaction with protonic acid decreased by 104.3 kJ mol⁻¹ compared with that of the reaction without it. The mechanism of reaction with catalyst protonic acid differs from that of reaction without it.

Keywords : Density functional theory, Biginelli reaction, (4*R*,5*S*,8*as*)-4,5,8*a*-triphenylhexahydropyrimido[4,5-*d*]pyrimidine-2,7(1*H*,3*H*)-dione, one-pot synthesis, transition state, reaction mechanism.

Introduction

In recent years, the Biginelli reaction is extensively used to the organic synthesis¹⁻¹². The Biginelli-type compound dihydropyrimidones show an attractive pharmacological profile as calcium channel blockers, antihypertensive agents, alpha-A-antagonists, and neuropeptide Y (NPY) antagonists¹³⁻¹⁸. One-pot synthesis method is used to the synthesis of dihydropyrimidones and their derivatives^{19,20}. (4*R*,5*S*,8*as*)-4,5,8*a*-Triphenylhexahydropyrimido[4,5-*d*]pyrimidine-2,7(1*H*,3*H*)-dione in from multi-component condensation of benzaldehyde, urea and acetophenone²¹. In the literature²¹, the Biginelli reaction of ethyl acetoacetate, an aromatic aldehyde, and urea could be efficiently catalyzed by potassium hydrogen sulfate (KHSO₄) in glycol, and the desired product was obtained in high yield. There is no literature about the mechanism of synthesis of (4*R*,5*S*,8*as*)-4,5,8*a*-triphenylhexahydropyrimido[4,5-*d*]pyrimidine-2,7(1*H*,3*H*)-dione. Atoms in

molecules (AIM) analysis was studied for the reaction mechanism synthesis of (4*R*,5*S*,8*as*)-4,5,8*a*-triphenylhexahydropyrimido[4,5-*d*]pyrimidine-2,7(1*H*,3*H*)-dione. The Quantum Theory of Atoms in Molecules (QTAIM) is a model of molecular and condensed matter electronic systems (such as crystals) in which the principal objects of molecular structure – atoms and bonds – are natural expressions of a system's observable electron density distribution function. An electron density distribution of a molecule is a probability distribution that describes the average manner in which the electronic charge is distributed throughout real space in the attractive field exerted by the nuclei. It is extensively used to research of the reaction mechanism^{22,23}. The main purposes of this paper are as follows : (1) to investigate the microscopic mechanism of reaction among benzaldehyde, urea and acetophenone for the synthesis of (4*R*,5*S*,8*as*)-4,5,8*a*-triphenylhexahydropyrimido[4,5-*d*]pyrimidine-2,7(1*H*,3*H*)-dione cata-

lyzed by protonic acid by way of density functional theory (DFT), (2) to confirm the rate-determining step of the reaction.

Computational methodology :

The mechanism of reaction among benzaldehyde, urea and acetophenone for the synthesis of (4*R*,5*S*,8*as*)-4,5,8*a*-triphenylhexahydropyrimido[4,5-*d*]pyrimidine-2,7-(1*H*,3*H*)-dione was investigated catalyzed by protonic acid by way of density functional theory (DFT). The geometries and the frequencies of reactants, intermediates, transition states and products were calculated at the B3LYP/6-311G(d) level²⁴. Stable structures were obtained. The parameters of geometry configuration are shown in Fig. 1 (R1-P2) and Fig. 2 (R1B-IM3D2). The vibration analysis and the IRC analysis proved the authenticity of intermedi-

ates and transition states. The reaction processes were confirmed by the changes of charge density at the bond-forming critical point (as shown by the numeric value in the parentheses in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2). All calculations were carried out with the Gaussian 03 program²⁵.

Results and discussion

The calculated energies (E) and relative energies (E_{rel}) of reactants, intermediates, transition states, and products are listed in Table 1. All energies (E) include zero-point energy (ZPE) corrections. Vibration frequencies of reactants, intermediates, and products are positive and those of all transition states have only one imaginary frequency. Fig. 3 is a schematic map of energy levels for the reaction without protonic acid and with protonic acid.

Fig. 1. Optimized geometric configurations of various compounds in the reaction : bond length in nanometers, bond angle in degree, charge density at bond-forming critical point in a.u.

Hu *et al.* : Theoretical study on the mechanism of synthesis of (4*R*,5*S*,8*as*)-4,5,8*a*- triphenylhexahydro- *etc.*

The reaction mechanism and energy analysis of the reaction without protonic acid :

The reaction between R1 and R2B for the synthesis of IM1A is a nucleophilic reaction. Firstly, the N4 atom of R2B attacks the carbonyl carbon atom of benzaldehyde to form intermediate IM1A through transition state TS1A. In TS1A, the bond length and the charge density at bond-forming critical point of N1-C2, N1-H3, and H3-O4 are 0.1567 nm and 0.2018 a.u., 0.1207 nm and 0.1805 a.u., and 0.1392 nm and 0.1058 a.u., respectively, and the

activation energy is 146.29 kJ mol⁻¹. IM1A forms intermediate IM1B through transition state TS1B. This is a hydrogen atom transfer process. In TS1B, the bond length and the charge density at the bond-forming critical point of N1-H2 are 0.1353 nm and 0.1218 a.u., respectively, and those of H2-O3 are 0.1310 nm and 0.1300 a.u., respectively, and the activation energy is 87.33 kJ mol⁻¹. The IM1B forms the IM1C and P1 through transition state TS1C. This is a dehydration process. In TS1C, the bond length and the charge density at bond-forming critical point

IM1C2

TS2A2

IM2A2

IM2B2

TS3A2

IM3A2

Fig. 2. Optimized geometric configurations of various compounds in the reaction : bond length in nanometers, bond angle in degree, charge density at bond-forming critical point in a.u.

Table 1. Energies (E) and relative energies (E_{rel}) of various species and imaginary frequency of transitions

Species	$-E$ (a.u.)	E_{rel} (kJ mol ⁻¹)	V (cm ⁻¹)
R1'(2R1+2R2B+R3B)	1526.35379	0	
TS1A'(R1+R2B+TS1A+R3B)	1526.29807	146.29	-1616.1
IM1A'(R1+R2B+IM1A+R3B)	1526.34833	14.33	
TS1B'(R1+R2B+TS1B+R3B)	1526.31507	101.66	-1919.08
IM1B'(R1+R2B+IM1B+R3B)	1526.39074	-97.01	
TS1C'(R1+R2B+TS1C+R3B)	1526.30962	115.98	-1799.54
IM1C'(R1+R2B+IM1C+R3B+P1)	1526.37167	-46.95	
TS2A'(R1+R2B+TS2A+P1)	1526.35268	2.91	-132.94
IM2A'(R1+R2B+IM2A+P1)	1526.40561	-136.05	
TS2B'(R1+R2B+TS2B+P1)	1526.30287	133.70	-2118.11
IM2B'(IM1C+IM2B+2P1)	1526.40662	-138.71	
TS3A'(TS3A+2P1)	1526.36789	-37.00	-122.55
IM3A'(IM3A+2P1)	1526.42753	-193.61	
TS3B'(TS3B+2P1)	1526.33286	54.95	-1732.68
IM3B'(IM3B+2P1)	1526.40658	-138.60	
TS3C'(TS3C+2P1)	1526.2978	147.01	-291.48
P2A'(P2+3P1)	1526.37712	-61.20	
R1'(2R1+2R2B+R3B+2R4)	1526.35379	0	
R1B'(2R1B+2R2B+R3B)	1527.06679	-1864.85	
TS1A2'(R1B+R2B+TS1A2+R3B)	1527.01039	-1717.34	-83.53
IM1A2'(R1B+R2B+IM1A2+R3B)	1527.04685	-1812.69	
TS1B2'(R1B+R2B+TS1B2+R3B)	1526.97755	-1631.43	-1851.91
IM1B2'(R1B+R2B+IM1B2+R3B)	1527.03726	-1787.62	
TS1C2'(R1B+R2B+TS1C2+R3B)	1526.99406	-1674.63	-1652.05
IM1C2'(R1B+R2B+IM1C2+R3B+P1)	1527.06814	-1868.37	
TS2A2'(R1B+R2B+TS2A2+P1)	1527.05418	-1831.86	-141.59
IM2A2'(R1B+R2B+IM2A2+P1)	1527.07002	-1873.30	
IM2B2'(R1B+R2B+IM2C2+2P1)	1526.78018	-1115.24	
TS3A2'(TS3A2+R4+2P1)	1526.77693	-1106.71	-233.19
IM3A2'(IM3A2+R4+2P1)	1526.78803	-1135.77	
TS3B2'(TS3B2+R4+2P1)	1526.74089	-1012.46	-108.21
IM3B2'(IM3B2+R4+2P1)	1526.74735	-1029.35	
TS3C2'(TS3C2+R4+2P1)	1526.71417	-942.57	-1729.75
IM3C2'(IM3C2+R4+2P1)	1526.7618	-1067.15	
TS3D2'(TS3D2+R4+3P1)	1526.7160	-947.58	-208.88
IM3D2'(IM3D2+R4+3P1)	1526.7181	-952.84	
P2B'(P2+3P1+2R4)	1526.37712	-61.0	

of N1-H2, H2-O3, and O3-C4 are 0.1376 nm and 0.1189 a.u., 0.1209 nm and 0.1668 a.u., and 0.1756 nm and 0.1168 a.u., respectively, and the activation energy is 212.99 kJ mol⁻¹. The mechanism of the reaction is : R1 + R2B → TS1A → IM1A → TS1B → IM1B → TS1C +

IM1C + H₂O.

IM1C reacts with R3B to form intermediate IM2A through transition state TS2A. This is a concerted reaction processes with the forming bond of C1-C5 and the transfer of a hydrogen atom. A hydrogen atom of hy-

Fig. 3. Schematic map of energy levels in the reaction.

droxyl of R3B is transferred to nitrogen atom of IM1C in this processes. In TS2A, the bond length and the charge density at bond-forming critical point of C1-C5 are 0.2865 nm and 0.0176 a.u., respectively, and those of H3-O4 are 0.1638 nm and 0.0572 a.u., respectively, and the activation energy is 49.86 kJ mol⁻¹. IM2A then forms intermediate IM2B through transition state TS2B, and this is a hydrogen atom transfer processes. In TS2B, the bond length and the charge density at bond-forming critical point of C1-H2 are 0.1553 nm and 0.0890 a.u., respectively, and those of H2-O3 are 0.1223 nm and 0.1594 a.u., respectively, and the activation energy is 269.75 kJ mol⁻¹. The mechanism of the reaction is : IM1C + R3B → TS2A → IM2A → TS2B → IM2B.

IM2B reacts with IM1C to form intermediate IM3A through transition state TS3A. This is also a concerted reaction process with the forming bond of C1-C2 and the transfer of a hydrogen atom. A hydrogen atom of hydroxyl of IM2B is transferred to nitrogen atom of IM1C in this processes. In TS3A, the bond length and the charge density at bond-forming critical point of C1-C2 are 0.2698 nm and 0.0241 a.u., respectively, and those of H3-O4 are 0.1749 nm and 0.0447 a.u., respectively, and the activation energy is 101.71 kJ mol⁻¹. IM3A then forms intermediate IM3B through transition state TS3B. This is a concerted reaction process with the closing a ring and the transfer of a hydrogen atom. In TS3B, the bond length and the charge density at bond-forming critical point of O1-H2 are 0.1420 nm and 0.1003 a.u., respectively, and those of H2-N3 are 0.1244 nm and 0.1638 a.u., respec-

tively, and the activation energy is 248.56 kJ mol⁻¹. IM3B then forms P1 and P2 through transition state TS3C. This is a concerted reaction process with the closing a ring and dehydration process. In TS3C, the bond length and the charge density at bond-forming critical point of N3-C4, C4-O1, and O1-H2 are 0.1803 nm and 0.1228 a.u., 0.2821 nm, and 0.1592 nm and 0.0615 a.u., respectively, and the activation energy is 285.60 kJ mol⁻¹. This is a rate-determining step. The mechanism of the reaction is : IM2B + IM1C → TS3A → IM3A → TS3B → IM3B → TS3C → P2 + H₂O.

The overall reaction is : 2R1 + 2R2B + R3B → P2 + 3H₂O, and the activation energy of the reaction is 285.60 kJ mol⁻¹.

The details of the reaction mechanism of the reaction are shown as Fig. 4.

The reaction mechanism and energy analysis of the reaction with catalyst protonic acid :

Firstly, R1 reacts with hydrogen proton to form R1B. R1B reacts with R2B to form IM1A2 through transition state TS1A2. In TS1A2, the bond length of C1-N2 is 0.2901 nm, the activation energy is 147.50 kJ mol⁻¹. IM1A2 then forms intermediate IM1B2 through transition state TS1B2. This is a hydrogen atom transfer processes. In TS1B2, the bond length and the charge density at the bond-forming critical point of O3-H4 are 0.1283 nm and 0.1369 a.u., respectively, and those of H4-N2 are 0.1383 nm and 0.1199 a.u., respectively, and the activation energy is 181.26 kJ mol⁻¹. This is a rate-determining step. IM1B2 forms intermediate IM1C2 through transition state TS1C2. This is a dehydration processes. In TS1C2, the bond length and the charge density at bond-forming critical point of H1-O2, O2-C4, and N3-H1 are 0.1219 nm and 0.1588 a.u., 0.1520 nm and 0.2021 a.u., and 0.1364 nm and 0.1239 a.u., respectively, and the activation energy is 112.99 kJ mol⁻¹. The mechanism of the reaction is : R1 + H⁺ → R1B; R1B + R2B → TS1A2 → IM1A2 → TS1B2 → IM1B2 → TS1C2 + H₂O.

IM1C2 reacts with R3B to form IM2A2 through transition state TS2A2. In TS2A2, the bond length and the charge density at the bond-forming critical point of C1-C2 are 0.2345 nm and 0.0618 a.u., respectively, and the activation energy is 36.51 kJ mol⁻¹. IM2A2 forms IM2B2

Fig. 4. The mechanism of the reaction with no catalyst.

and R4 directly. The mechanism of the reaction is : $IM1C2 + R3B \rightarrow TS2A2 \rightarrow IM2A2 \rightarrow IM2B2 + H^+$.

IM2B2 reacts with IM1C2 to form IM3A2 through transition state TS3A2. In TS3A2, the bond length and the charge density at the bond-forming critical point of C1-C2 are 0.2213 nm and 0.0568 a.u., respectively, and the activation energy is 8.53 kJ mol⁻¹. IM3A2 then forms intermediate IM3B2 through transition state TS3B2. This is a closing the ring processes. In TS3B2, the bond length and the charge density at the bond-forming critical point of N1-C2 are 0.2174 nm and 0.0554 a.u., respectively, and the activation energy is 123.31 kJ mol⁻¹. IM3B2 forms intermediate IM3C2 and P1 through transition state TS3C2. This is a concerted reaction process with transferring the hydrogen atom and dehydration process. In TS3C2, the bond length and the charge density at bond-forming critical point of N1-H2 are 0.1343 nm and 0.1300 a.u., respectively, and those of H2-O3 are 0.1239 nm and 0.1510

a.u., respectively, and the activation energy is 86.78 kJ mol⁻¹. IM3C2 then forms intermediate IM3D2 through transition state TS3D2. In TS3D2, the bond length and the charge density at the bond-forming critical point of C1-N2 are 0.1943 nm and 0.0902 a.u., respectively, and the activation energy is 119.56 kJ mol⁻¹. IM3D2 forms P2 and R4 directly. The mechanism of the reaction is : $IM2B2 + IM1C2 \rightarrow TS2A2 \rightarrow IM2A2 \rightarrow IM2B2 \rightarrow TS3A2 \rightarrow IM3A2 \rightarrow TS3B2 \rightarrow IM3B2 \rightarrow TS3C2 \rightarrow IM3C2 + H_2O \rightarrow TS3D2 + H_2O \rightarrow IM3D2 + H_2O \rightarrow P2 + H_2O + H^+$.

The overall reaction is : $2R1 + 2R2B + R3B + 2R4 \rightarrow P2 + 3H_2O + 2R4$, and the activation energy of the reaction is 181.26 kJ mol⁻¹. The activation energy of reaction with protonic acid decreased by 104.34 kJ mol⁻¹ compared with that of the reaction without protonic acid.

The details of the reaction mechanism of the reaction are shown as Fig. 5.

Hu *et al.* : Theoretical study on the mechanism of synthesis of (4*R*,5*S*,8*as*)-4,5,8*a*- triphenylhexahydro- *etc.*

Fig. 5. The mechanism of the reaction with catalyst protonic acid.

Conclusions

The microscopic mechanism of reaction among benzaldehyde, urea and acetophenone for the synthesis of (4*R*,5*S*,8*as*)-4,5,8*a*-triphenylhexahydropyrimido[4,5-*d*]pyrimidine-2,7(1*H*,3*H*)-dione catalyzed by protonic acid and without protonic acid was investigated by DFT. At

the same time, characteristic of catalyst protonic acid was investigated. The following was shown : (1) Protonic acid is an effective catalyst in the synthesis of (4*R*,5*S*,8*as*)-4,5,8*a*-triphenylhexahydropyrimido[4,5-*d*]pyrimidine-2,7(1*H*,3*H*)-dione from benzaldehyde, urea and acetophenone. (2) The activation energy with protonic acid de-

creased by 104.34 kJ mol⁻¹ compared with that of the reaction without it. (3) The mechanism of reaction with catalyst protonic acid differs from that of without it. (4) It is identical with Shi *et al.*'s conclusions¹⁵, and the mechanism of the reaction is the same as that of Biginelli and other authors¹⁻⁵.

Acknowledgements

We thank the Scientific Research Foundation of the Science & Technology Bureau of Dahou for financial support (2013(5)).

References

1. P. Biginelli, *Ber.*, 1891, **24**, 1317.
2. P. Biginelli, *Ber.*, 1893, **26**, 447.
3. C. O. Kappe, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2000, **10**, 49.
4. X. H. Chen, X. Y. Xu, H. Liu, L. F. Cun and L. Z. Gong, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **128**, 14802.
5. V. Polshettiwar and R. S. Varma, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 2007, **48**, 7343.
6. L. Z. Gong, X. H. Chen and X. Y. Xu, *Chemistry – A European Journal*, 2007, **13**, 8920.
7. N. Ahmed and J. E. van Lier, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 2007, **48**, 5407.
8. A. Debache, M. Amimour, A. Belfaitah, S. Rhouti and B. Carboni, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 2008, **49**, 6119.
9. R. Wang and Z. Q. Liu, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2012, **77**, 3952.
10. J. H. Clark, D. J. Macquarrie and J. Sherwood, *Chemistry – A European Journal*, 2013, **19**, 5174.
11. I. Sehout, R. Boulcina, B. Boumoud, F. Berree, B. Carboni and A. Debache, *Letters in Organic Chemistry*, 2013, **10**, 463.
12. H. G. Alvim, T. B. de Lima, H. C. de Oliveira, F. C. Gozzo, J. L. de Macedo, P. V. Abdelnur and B. A. Neto, *ACS Catalysis*, 2013, **3**, 1420.
13. S. R. Alapati, P. K. Pallela, P. Rangappa and V. Pillarisetti, US patent, US7687511 B2, 2010.
14. K. S. Atwai, B. N. Swanson, S. E. Unger, D. M. Floyd, S. Moreland, A. Hedberg and B. C. O'Reilly, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1991, **34**, 806.
15. G. C. Rovnyak, K. S. Atwal, A. Hedberg, S. D. Kimball, S. Moreland, J. Z. Gougoutas, B. C. O'Reilly, J. Schwart and M. F. Malley, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1992, **35**, 3254.
16. G. J. Grover, S. Dzwonczyk, D. M. McMullen, C. S. Normadinam, P. G. Slenph and S. J. Moreland, *J. Cardiovasc. Pharmacol.*, 1995, **26**, 289.
17. S. Putatunda, S. Chakraborty, S. Ghosh, P. Nandi, S. Chakraborty, P. C. Sen and A. Chakraborty, *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 2012, **54**, 223.
18. S. S. Kshirsagar and P. Shanmugasundaram, *Synthesis*, 2013, **5**, 2899.
19. Y. M. Litvinov, A. A. Shestopalov, L. A. Rodinovskaya and A. M. Shestopalov, *Journal of Combinatorial Chemistry*, 2009, **11**, 914.
20. Z. L. Shen, X. P. Xu and S. J. Ji, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2010, **75**, 1162.
21. F. Shi, R. H. Jia, X. J. Zhang, S. J. Tu, S. Yan, Y. Zhang, B. Jiang, J. Y. Zhang and C. S. Yao, *Synthesis*, 2007, **18**, 2782.
22. R. F. W. Bader, "Atoms in Molecules : A Quantum Theory", Clarendon, Oxford, UK, 1990.
23. P. L. Ppeliier, "Atoms in Molecules : An Introduction", Pearson Education, Halow, UK, 1999.
24. M. Takahashi, S. Tsutsui, K. Sakamoto, M. Kira, T. Müller and Y. Apeloig, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2001, **123**, 347.
25. M. J. Frisch, G. W. Trucks, H. B. Schlegel, G. E. Scuseria, M. A. Robb, J. R. Cheeseman, J. A. Montgomery (Jr.), T. Vreven, K. N. Kudin, J. C. Burant, J. M. Millam, S. S. Iyengar, J. Tomasi, V. Barone, B. Mennucci, M. Cossi, G. Scalmani, N. Rega, G. A. Petersson, H. Nakatsuji, M. Hada, M. Ehara, K. Toyota, R. Fukuda, J. Hasegawa, M. Ishida, T. Nakajima, Y. Honda, O. Kitao, H. Nakai, M. Klene, X. Li, J. E. Knox, H. P. Hratchian, J. B. Cross, C. Adamo, J. Jaramillo, R. Gomperts, R. E. Stratmann, O. Yazyev, A. J. Austin, R. Cammi, C. Pomelli, J. W. Ochterski, P. Y. Ayala, K. Morokuma, G. A. Voth, P. Salvador, J. J. Dannenberg, V. G. Zakrzewski, S. Dapprich, A. D. Daniels, M. C. Strain, O. Farkas, D. K. Malick, A. D. Rabuck, K. Raghavachari, J. B. Foresman, J. V. Ortiz, Q. Cui, A. G. Baboul, S. Clifford, J. Cioslowski, B. B. Stefanov, G. Liu, A. Liashenko, P. Piskorz, I. Komaromi, R. L. Martin, D. J. Fox, T. Keith, M. A. Al-Laham, C. Y. Peng, A. Nanayakkara, M. Challacombe, P. M. W. Gill, B. Johnson, W. Chen, M. W. Wong, C. Gonzalez and J. A. Pople, Gaussian, Inc., Pittsburgh, PA, 2003.